
CLIMATE AND ENERGY RELATED NORMS AND ATTITUDES - INTRODUCING THE CERNA ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted within the framework of a H2020 project, PROBONO, which aims to create Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs). A GBN is a neighbourhood where energy-positive, zero-emission buildings are integrated at a delimited area or district level. A GBN incorporates green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, stakeholders' engagement and behaviours to ensure a just transition that maximises the economic and social co-benefits. The present study takes a social scientific approach to assess existing attitudes, norms, knowledge or misconceptions around climate and energy-related issues and legislative principles across the six participating European countries in the project. For this purpose, the CERNA (Climate and Energy Related Norms and Attitudes) tool was created to examine participants' factual knowledge, assumptions about others' knowledge and attitudes, and the influence of social norms and political ideologies on climate perceptions. Pluralistic ignorance, the shared misconception of others' opinions, poses barriers to behaviour change and policy acceptance. Effective interventions however, such as leveraging social norms, can promote pro-environmental attitudes. This tool is meant to provide aid in discovering underlying social and psychological factors before implementing interventions to ensure long-term success. The CERNA survey offers a new diagnostic, social-psychological approach to understanding environmental behaviour, aiming to inform targeted interventions and maximize policy impact. This paper presents the background, structure, and purpose of the CERNA tool, along with a preliminary exploration of its findings. The survey was conducted across six EU countries, with this article focusing on initial results from Ireland. Broader insights from the remaining countries are briefly outlined in the Discussion section.

Keywords pluralistic ignorance; social norms; climate change; energy; attitudes

1 Introduction

When talking about the green transition, there is no unified set of solutions. The culture, the socio-economic circumstances, politicians, and policies are vastly different in each country. Therefore, we need to start at step one: assessing the situation as is, by measuring what do people know (or think they know) about climate and energy related issues within each their contexts, what are the initial attitudes that we would address. For this, we have created the CERNA (Climate and Energy related Norms and Attitudes) assessment, to be used as a diagnostic tool in different societal contexts.

When it comes to supporting people in adapting their behaviour and making more sustainable, climate-friendly and energy-efficient choices, providing information alone is rarely sufficient (Cadario and Chandon, 2020). Human behaviour and decision-making are not solely shaped by information. Behaviours and attitudes are shaped by multiple contextual determinants such as perceived social norms, contextual cues, framing, etc. (Bicchieri and Sontuoso, 2020; Latkin et al., 2013). A large body of research shows that cognitive heuristics systematically affect how people interpret information, form judgments, and act in everyday situations (Olaborode and Walt, 2021; Ahmad et al., 2020). These

are strategies that use only a small fraction of the available information. This makes our decision very rapid, which is incredibly useful in evolutionary terms, to survive approaching danger, for instance. Fortunately, most of the time the result of using automatic heuristic thinking is “good enough”, however in certain situations they lead to poor judgments. We might think of these as “errors in judgement” while in psychological literature they are commonly known as cognitive biases (Ellis, 2018).

Certain cognitive biases, e.g., the false consensus effect (our tendency to overestimate how many people agree with our own beliefs), the misinformation effect (our memory of events is heavily influenced by how that event is represented, for example in media), the availability heuristic (our tendency of estimating the probability of something based on the examples that we are aware of), or the optimism bias (underestimating the probability of bad things happening to us but overestimating the good) are all factors we need to consider and address when we would like to change energy and environment related behaviour (Zhang et al., 2020). The CERNA tool provides a diagnostic framework that maps factual knowledge, perceived social norms, and pluralistic ignorance related to climate and energy issues. Rather than relying solely on top-down policy mechanisms, this approach seeks to inform both policymakers and citizens by identifying misalignments between individual attitudes and perceived collective beliefs. Drawing on insights from social norms theory and game theory, we recognize that many climate-related behaviours involve coordination problems, where inaccurate beliefs about others’ attitudes and actions can hinder collective progress (Basar, 2013; Przepiorka, 2023; Wade and Griffiths, 2021; Mazutis and Eckardt, 2017).

Awareness, however, in many cases can be the first step towards the adaptation of more sustainable behaviours. (Park et al., 2023). Public engagement is a two-way dialogue. Before intervening, we need to listen; assess knowledge and attitudes, understand interests and barriers to action through social scientific research. This will inform us about our starting point and allow us to plan meaningful interventions, targeted at the identified gaps in public understanding of climate issues.

We reviewed several established surveys in the field, including (but not limited to) the US Climate Culture Index, the Planetary Health Action Survey, and the PARCA Longitudinal Study. While these instruments are highly valuable within their respective scopes, we identified the need for a more comprehensive tool to fully address our specific objectives. As a result, we developed the CERNA tool, inspired by available literature on Energy literacy assessment, Climate Change literacy assessment, social norm scales, and assessment on Pluralistic Ignorance related to climate issues. The aim of the survey is to map existing (mis-)conceptions of the most impactful energy- and climate behaviours, allowing us to target behavioural change interventions where they will have the biggest impact. The novelty of our approach also lies in the layers of our assessment, given that social norms and pluralistic ignorance are measured in different social proximities: people important to you, people in your city, people in your country, and people in the EU. This gives us a deeper insight to the societal dynamics that shape our perceptions, attitudes, and possibly our behaviours. The paper will briefly discuss all components, but will focus primarily on the assessment of pluralistic ignorance.

1.1 Pluralistic Ignorance

The aim of the CERNA survey is to assess not only factual knowledge, but also assumptions about the knowledge and attitudes of other people. Social cognition research suggests that human behaviour is dependent on our subjective representation of reality, which is influenced by our perception and interpretation of surrounding. Our decisions and actions are largely influenced by what we perceive is the “social norm”, especially if that is perceived as the norm of a group we strongly identify with (national, political, generational, etc.) (Farrow, Grolleau and Ibanez, 2017). When it comes to environmental issues, the underestimation of interest and awareness of our peers can be a huge barrier to action. The literature calls this phenomenon pluralistic ignorance, which is a shared misconception on how others think or act (Park et al., 2023). According to a recent study, people vastly underestimate the public support for climate policies, and climate concern. While two thirds of the participants supported the policies, they estimated the supporters to be only one third of the population. Even though supporters of the climate action outnumber opponents two-to-one, these results have concerning implications. First, the underestimation of public willingness to discuss climate issues obstruct actions and behaviour change - in democratic models of governance, politicians are unlikely to propose climate actions without public support (Walker, Kurz and Russel, 2018). Second, overestimation of opposition to climate policies pressures us to oppose them as well, diminishing motivations towards the green transition. The absence of knowledge on the consensus around environmental issues gives way to polarization, which means these misperceptions will bring a self-fulfilling prophecy: not realizing the true level of support of climate action may in fact lead to decreased support in the future (Sparkman, Geiger and Weber, 2022).

Social norm interventions have been shown to be effective in reducing energy consumption in field experiments. The use of social norms in information provision, (informing people about others’ behaviours and attitudes), and other types of peer influence interventions could be leveraged by policy makers to target pro-environmental attitudes (Farrow, Grolleau and Ibanez, 2017).

As Hansen (2018) pointed out, when it comes to addressing behaviour changes and policy making, before intervening, a precise diagnosis of the problem will no doubt increase the success of said interventions. Merely treating symptoms may have short-term effects (with potential side effects) but are also likely to lead to the regression to the status quo on the long run. With the above described three-component CERNA assessment survey we propose a diagnostic approach to a wide range of factors that influence environment and energy related behaviour. Understanding this is the first step to ensure that the planned interventions will be beneficial and understood by the targeted communities, and future policies will maximise their potential.

2 Methods

The CERNA assessment was created based on extensive literature review and in consideration of the project’s needs and intervention potential. It has four major sections, measuring: social norms, pluralistic ignorance, knowledge, and demographic data. The assessment was administered in all six cities of the participating project countries (Porto, Madrid, Dublin, Brussels, Aarhus Prague), with data gathering stretching from the spring of 2024 to early 2025. With the exception of Porto (where data was gathered with snowball method, N=83) we gathered representative data in age and gender from each city (N=400). In the case of Aarhus, Denmark, we gained representative data from the country (N=400), given the small size of the city and the available resources. We carried out statistical analysis using IBM SPSS software.

3 Results

In this paper, we are showcasing the potential of this new tool by presenting preliminary results from the data gathered in Dublin. However, data analysis has already started in all countries, which we will briefly address in the Discussion chapter. We examined pluralistic ignorance in two topics: general climate related concern, and support for certain environmental policies. First, we asked participants “How concerned are you about climate change?”, then “How concerned do you think the average person is about climate change in your close personal circles, your city, your country, and in the EU. Our results show that 66.9 percent of Dublin citizens are at least “Quite” or “Strongly” concerned, yet they estimate this number to be lower in each of these listed groups. They especially underestimate the level of climate concern on the city (Dublin) level, where they estimated that only 42.4 percent of people would share the same level of concern. Based on the representative data from Dublin, the discrepancy between individuals’ own reported climate concern and their estimation of others’ concern aligns with theoretical accounts of pluralistic ignorance and provides empirical support for its presence in this context.

Figure 1: Real and perceived climate concern of self and others in Dublin

3.1 Results on real and perceived policy support

In our second topic, policy support, we list three relevant environmental policies from the EU and asked people to first mark how much they themselves support this policy and then estimate what percentage of people would at least somewhat support these policies in their close personal circles, their city, their country and in the EU. Pluralistic ignorance proved to be present in connection with all three policies (Carbon Tax, Sustainable Public procurement of food, Renewable Energy Mandate). Figure 2 shows the example of the real and perceived support for the Sustainable Public procurement of food policy in Dublin.

Figure 2: Real and perceived policy support in Dublin

3.2 Results on Knowledge

We have asked the survey participants to rank some commonly recommended actions related to reducing energy consumption and climate footprint. In Figure 3 we show the correct order of these actions in terms of energy efficiency (green bars) compared to how participants view them (yellow bars). While there is a moderate, but non-significant correlation between the correct and perceived order of these actions ($r(398)=0.545$, $p > 0.05$), certain gaps are worth highlighting in terms of future intervention potential. For example, participants seem to overestimate the importance of turning off the lights when not in use, but they seem to underestimate certain actions that would have a much larger impact, such as shortening their shower time by two minutes.

Figure 3: Real and perceived order of energy saving actions in terms of efficiency

3.3 Results on Social Norms

The CERNA assessment measures both descriptive (what do I think other people do) and injunctive social norms (what do I think other people expect me to do) in relation to energy efficiency, and climate friendly behaviour. The interaction between injunctive and descriptive norms plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' motivation to engage in climate-positive behaviors. Studies have shown that people are more inclined to support climate policies when they believe their social group endorses such actions (ingroup injunctive norms), as opposed to merely observing what others are doing (descriptive norms) (Cole et al., 2022). While descriptive norms provide a reference point for typical behavior, injunctive norms influence behavior by signaling social approval, thereby encouraging alignment with perceived group expectations (Bhanot, 2021). According to our results in the topic of energy efficiency, descriptive norms are consistently perceived as stronger than injunctive norms. This suggests that, across all examined social proximities, people believe others behave less energy efficiently than what they themselves consider to be appropriate or ideal. Figure 4 shows the difference between the social proximities and the two types of norms in Dublin.

Figure 4: Social Norms in Dublin

4 Discussion

In this paper, our objective was to give a short overview of the CERNA assessment tool and its potential use in interpreting the social dynamics related to climate and energy related discussions. Our preliminary analysis shows very similar trends in all six countries we examined: in every single case, people show relatively high climate concern, high support for green policies, but they underestimate the same concern and support from others. There is cross-country variation in the extent of this underestimation, and in the social proximities where they are most salient. For example, in all examined countries, people estimate their own concern as highest, closely followed by "people in the EU", who, according to them, must be much more concerned, and supportive of climate policies, than the people of their own countries. An interesting exception is Brussels, where in terms of policy support, EU citizens are rated to show significantly lower support, than the self-reported one. In contrast, participants in Prague underestimated their fellow citizens the most, and EU citizens are viewed to have significantly higher concern than self. These results all point to the fact that perceptions, norms and attitudes around climate change are influenced by a complex interaction of social, political and cultural factors, that all need to be taken into account in order to design meaningful interventions in a specific city or country.

5 Conclusions

This preprint presents initial findings from Dublin using the CERNA assessment tool, highlighting the widespread presence of pluralistic ignorance in both climate concern and support for environmental policies. Our preliminary cross-country comparisons suggest that while high levels of individual concern and policy support are common, people consistently underestimate these sentiments in others, particularly within their own cities and countries. These insights underscore the importance of social perception in shaping public discourse and potential climate action. Our upcoming publication will explore these findings in greater depth, focusing on their interactions, cross-cultural patterns, and implications for climate communication and policy design.

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7 References

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